

Students' Perception of and Attitude to Online Teaching During Covid-19 Lockdown at Babcock University

AUTHOR(S): BANKOLE, Adelola Mojisola (RN, RM, ROPHN, BNSc, M.Sc.)

AND

Prof. ONIFADE Comfort

Abstract

Universities in Nigeria have adopted online teaching and learning as a response to Covid-19 pandemic emergency. This study examined students' perception of online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown, described the students' attitude to online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown and assessed the relationship between students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown at Babcock University. The study used the survey research design. The sampling technique employed was multi stage sampling procedure to draw sample size of 365 for this study because of the need for effective coverage of the large population. Structured questionnaire was administered to Babcock University Undergraduates in printed form in order to obtain useful information which are in line with the objectives of this study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The findings revealed students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown was 69.8, which was high. The study also revealed that students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown was moderate and good. It could then be said that online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown depends on the effective utilization of ICTs. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that organizational innovative climate should be created by the university administrator which must influence lecturers' use of information technology.

E.G.C.S.J

Accepted 20 April 2021

Published 30 April 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5048477

Keywords: Students Perception, Attitude, Online Teaching, Covid-19,

**ABOUT
AUTHOR**

Author(s): **BANKOLE, Adelola Mojisola (RN, RM, ROPHN, BNSc, M.Sc.)**
Federal Medical Centre, PMB 3031, Sapon, Abeokuta, Nigeria.

And

Prof. ONIFADE Comfort
Communication and General Studies,
Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria

Introduction

The recent outbreak of Covid-19 has created educational disruptions, and global health concerns which have proven very difficult to manage by global health systems. This is evident in the gaps which the Corona virus pandemic increased in the education sector globally especially with the negative effects it has on pupils from poor socioeconomic backgrounds who have been unable to learn since the outbreak. Though, the Corona virus pandemic is novel, it already has toxic effects on humanity. As at now, no nation or race across the world is immune from the Corona virus pandemic, and the entire world seems overwhelmed by the speed of the spread and its devastating effects. This is saddening considering the fact that the Corona virus pandemic has no boundaries, and the effect is large and fast. Just within few months of the outbreak of the disease, it has drastically changed the lifestyles of the entire world with billions of people being forced to 'stay at home', 'observe self-isolations', and work and learn from home. It has limited the freedom of people to move, trade or associate.

From inception to now, the attainment of educational objectives in the Nigerian University system has been achieved through non electronic teaching and learning methodologies. Dobbs et al. (2017) posited that the traditional educational system required having students on campus and taking lectures, examinations, seminars and other academic assignments in classrooms in physical buildings. The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic has necessitated the adoption of online education by Universities across the world. Hodges et al. (2020) refer to this temporary shift of instructional delivery to an alternate delivery mode due to crisis circumstance as Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT). However, for Universities in developing countries like Nigeria, the traditional instruction delivery methods may not be retained post Covid-19.

De Paepe et al. (2018) defined online learning and described it as a learning process that is created through the interaction with network-based content delivered through digital platforms. According to Tseng and Walsh (2011), effective online learning may be best achieved by thorough understanding of the educational needs of students and specifically of those who want to take advantage of the Internet and the number of applications and technological devices which can be used to enhance their learning experiences. Nakumura (2017) emphasize that online learning can be extremely beneficial because it promotes wider access to college education with reduced time and cost in commuting. The Internet gives students the liberty to choose the learning facility and the schedule most convenient for them as far as time, distance, flexibility, and money are concerned. Overall, the major questions in the debate on the validity of online learning has been answered; with the help of the technologically advanced forms of learning through computers, related devices, and internet. Also, the effectiveness of online programs to educate and retain students is similar to the traditional classroom learning format (Bradley, et al., 2017).

Atayero (2020) observed that Universities in Nigeria have adopted online teaching and learning as a response to Covid-19 pandemic emergency; he further noted that this trend will continue till post Covid-19, as it has opened Universities to educational opportunities, which were not hitherto considered. Nigeria Universities may adopt blended learning methodologies – a combination of traditional instructional delivery and online teaching methods; they may also extend online teaching to holiday periods, when the students are at home. Some universities may even venture into online certificate programs. Thus, this study

proposed to investigate students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University.

Very little research has been conducted, especially in developing countries, to explore students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. There is even less research that focuses on students' attitude to online teaching during covid-19 lockdown. Therefore, the present study proposed to investigate students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University. This study specifically:

1. examined the students' perception of online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;
2. described the students' attitude to online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;
3. examined the differences in male and female students' perception of online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;
4. determined the differences in male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown; and
5. assessed the relationship between students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during COVID-19 lockdown at Babcock University.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?
2. What is the students' attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Research Hypotheses

These hypotheses were postulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University.
2. There is no significant difference in male and female students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.
3. There is no significant difference in male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Methodology

This research study used the survey research design. The subjects of interest were undergraduates of Babcock University. As found in the university's website, the university has a student population of Seven thousand, two hundred and seventy nine students (7270). The sample size of 365 for this study were determined by applying the Cochran (1997) and multi stage sampling procedure was employed to draw sample for this study because of the need for effective coverage of the large population.

The structured questionnaire was administered to Babcock University Undergraduates in printed form in order to obtain useful information which is in line with the objectives of this study. The questionnaire was divided into three sections; section A which entails the demographics of the respondent such as gender, level, age, and course of study, section B was structured to determine the students perception of online teaching and section C addressed the students' attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University. The face validity and the content validity methods were adopted.

The questionnaire was self-administered by the researcher with the aid of two research assistants. The researcher visited Babcock University with a letter of introduction. This letter was taken to the University Registrar to secure permission to carry out the study in the University. A period of one week was used for the administration of instrument and collection of data. The results were presented using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Table 1: Students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

Items	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Undecided (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Perceived self-efficacy of using e-learning					
I feel confident using the e-learning system.	114 (31.2)	112 (30.7)	61 (16.7)	38 (10.4)	40 (11.0)
I feel confident operating e-learning functions.	124 (34.0)	111 (30.4)	35 (9.6)	54 (14.8)	41 (11.2)
I feel confident using online learning content.	108 (29.6)	123 (33.7)	39 (10.7)	51 (14.0)	44 (12.1)
Perceived enjoyment of using e-learning:					
I enjoy online teaching and learning.	100 (27.4)	102 (27.9)	68 (18.6)	63 (17.3)	32 (8.8)
I enjoy using e-learning functions.	94 (25.8)	105 (28.8)	72 (19.7)	56 (15.3)	10.4 (9.8)
I am satisfied with learning online content.	107 (29.3)	89 (24.4)	76 (20.8)	57 (15.6)	36 (9.9)
I enjoy multimedia instructions.	104 (28.5)	102 (27.9)	41 (11.2)	74 (20.3)	40 (11.0)
Perceived usefulness of using e-learning:					
I believe e-learning content is informative.	118 (32.3)	82 (22.5)	65 (17.8)	63 (17.3)	27 (7.4)
I believe e-learning is a useful learning tool.	91 (24.9)	94 (25.8)	93 (25.5)	54 (14.8)	33 (9.1)
I believe e-learning content is useful.	112 (30.7)	85 (23.3)	61 (16.7)	70 (19.2)	37 (10.1)
Behavioural intention of using e-learning:					
I intend to use e-learning to assist my learning.	112 (30.7)	98 (26.9)	54 (14.8)	49 (13.4)	52 (14.2)
I intend to use e-learning content to assist my learning.	89 (24.4)	116 (31.8)	65 (17.8)	57 (15.6)	38 (10.4)
I intend to use e-learning as an autonomous learning tool.	95 (26.0)	105 (28.8)	88 (24.1)	55 (15.1)	22 (6.0)
Weighted % = 69.77					

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The weighted percentage of students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown in Table 1 was 69.8, which was high. Majority 61.9% of the students agreed they were confident using the e-learning system, 64.4% felt confident operating e-learning functions, 63.3% felt confident using online learning content. The table further shows that 55.3%) enjoyed online teaching and learning, 54.5% enjoyed using e-learning functions, 53.7% satisfied with learning online content, and 56.4% enjoyed multimedia instructions. Most 54.8% of the respondents believe e-learning content is informative, 50.7% believed e-learning is a useful learning tool, 54% believed e-learning content is useful, 57.5% intended to use e-learning to assist my learning, 56.2% intended to use e-learning content to assist my learning, and 54.8% intended to use e-learning as an autonomous learning tool.

Research Question 2: What is the students' attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Table 2: Students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

Item	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Undecided (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
If given a choice I would prefer onsite learning to online learning.	93 (25.4)	139 (38.1)	93 (25.5)	27 (7.4)	13 (3.6)
Finding my way around a Web Site is harder than finding my way around a physical learning environment.	92 (25.2)	124 (34.0)	104 (28.5)	29 (7.9)	24 (6.6)
It is difficult to understand online learning without getting acquainted with appropriate guidance	112 (30.7)	100 (27.4)	106 (29.0)	52 (14.2)	18 (4.9)
It is difficult to favor online learning on regular basis due to least face to face interaction among students and teachers	92 (25.2)	94 (25.8)	93 (25.5)	83 (22.7)	26 (7.1)
Expression of thoughts and notions is a hectic job in terms of writing via online learning	91 (24.9)	109 (29.9)	100 (27.4)	52 (14.2)	13 (3.6)
Learning of courses through online portal is difficult	91 (24.9)	123 (33.7)	101 (27.7)	30 (8.2)	20 (5.5)
University should provide better platform for learning via direct interaction among students and teachers rather than by using online	112 (30.7)	117 (32.1)	87 (23.8)	45 (12.3)	4 (1.1)
Slow computer and poor internet connections discouraged me to	98 (26.8)	126	78 (21.4)	51	12 (3.3)

use online learning		(34.5)		(14.0)	
Weighted % = 55.81					

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The weighted percentage of students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown was 55.81, which was moderate. Majority 63.6% of the students agreed that if they were given a choice I would prefer onsite learning to online learning; 59.2% found their way around a Web Site is harder than finding my way around a physical learning environment; 58.1% agreed that it is difficult to understand online learning without getting acquainted with appropriate guidance; and 51% found it difficult to favor online learning on regular basis due to least face to face interaction among students and teachers. Also, 54.8% consented that expression of thoughts and notions is a hectic job in terms of writing via online learning; 58.6% agreed that learning of courses through online portal is difficult; 62.7% said university should provide better platform for learning via direct interaction among students and teachers rather than by using online; and 61.4% agreed that slow computer and poor internet connections discouraged me to use online learning.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the students' perception of and attitude to online teaching

		Perception	Attitude
Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	.426
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.009
	N	365	365
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.426	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	
	N	365	365

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The results presented in Table 4 revealed a significant relationship ($r = .426$; $p = .009 < .05$). This shows that students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown has significant and positive relationship with their attitude to online teaching. Also, when the coefficient valued $r = .426$ is translated into a percentage, it was revealed that 42.6% of their attitude to online teaching was accounted for by their perception of online teaching. Therefore, the earlier stated hypothesis that "There is no significant difference between students' perception of and attitude to online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown at Babcock University" could not be sustained but rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in male and female students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 4: Independent t-test to show the difference between male and female students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	Mean diff	P value
Male	167	37.51	6.98	1.36	363	1.506	1.37	.123
Female	198	38.88	6.17	1.23				

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4 presents the result of hypothesis two postulated in this study. It is indicated that there is no significant difference between male and female students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown (Mean difference = 1.37, $t_{(363)} = 1.506$, $p = .123$). Going through the mean scores, one can say that there is no significant difference between male (N = 167, Mean = 37.51, Std. dev. = 6.98) and the female (N = 198, Mean = 38.88, Std. dev. = 6.17). Based on this, the earlier set hypothesis is retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5: Independent t-test to show the difference between male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	Mean diff	P value
Male	167	25.93	3.71	1.01	363	1.109	0.54	.621
Female	198	26.47	3.63	0.98				

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 6 presents the result of hypothesis two postulated in this study. It is indicated that there is no significant difference in male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown (Mean difference = 0.54, $t_{(363)} = 1.109$, $p = .621$). Going through the mean scores, one can say that there is no significant difference between male (N = 167, Mean = 25.93, Std. dev. = 3.71) and the female (N = 198, Mean = 26.47, Std. dev. = 3.63). Based on this, the earlier set hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in male and female students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Discussion

The students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown was 69.8, which was high. For instance, majority of the students agreed they were confident using the e-learning system, felt confident operating e-learning functions, and felt confident using online learning content. It is in line with the result of the study conducted by Mustafa (2015) who stated that students do not feel bored when they learn through Edmodo. Using social

media tools can develop students' learning experience since they increased the level of students' engagement in improving students' educational outcomes (Alahmari, 2017). The platform also breaks their learning routine and it motivate them to interact and share information between peers. Working with computer will make students learn more quickly, show greater retention, and are better motivated to learn (Kurt & Yildirim, 2018). The use of technology can gain students' interest because it satisfies their technology addiction. The digital-native students can be interested in learning because they like the fact that they utilize technology in the classroom (Mustafa, 2015).

The outcome of this study revealed that students' attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown was moderate and good. It could then be said that online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown depends on the effective utilization of ICTs. It has been proved that a positive attitude is created when students are not afraid to engage with ICT tools. It was found that the use of new technologies contributed to the development of a positive attitude for students. This is in tandem with the findings of Ashong and Commander (2012) in their study with Anglo-Saxon and Asian, which found that there was an important impact on the students' attitudes toward online learning. From the significant differences found in the two races/ethnicities, they identified that it is necessary to develop a unique online learning approach that will address the appropriate online learning needs of the two races/ethnicities.

This study is equally similar to that of Edward (2018) in study on the relationship between college student attitudes towards online learning based on reading self-efficacy, ethnicity, and age. She found that the students' attitude toward online learning was good and also being affected positively by reading self-efficacy. However, most students have spent their entire academic lives in traditional classes where interaction and immediate feedback from instructors and peers are more common. These concerns may be why students perceive they would lose a familiar type of interaction and have to engage with classroom participants in a new and different way (Carver & Kosloski Jr., 2015).

The results revealed that students' perception of online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown has significant and positive relationship with their attitude to online teaching. The implication here might be that the interest level and engagement with new technologies by Nigerian students may help explain the favourable perception the participants had toward online teaching, which equally is reflecting in their attitude. A study by Costa, Faria and Neto (2018) found that 90% of Portuguese students use new technologies and 69% of them use new technologies more than an hour and a half a day.

It was indicated that there is no significant difference between male and female students' perception of and attitude towards online teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. This is because being a male or female has nothing to do with online learning and teaching. This is corroborated with the findings of Peck, et al., (2018) who found that students were more likely to be motivated if they clearly understood what is expected of them, rather than being motivated by relationships with instructors. Hannay and Newvine (2006) concluded that learner-content interaction plays the most important role in ensuring that online students are successful

Conclusion

This study showed that online teaching and learning is a valuable method of teaching students. In the opinion of the respondents in this study, online teaching and learning is effective in increasing knowledge and is highly accepted. The students that participated in the study perceive online learning platforms as a user-friendly learning tool which encourage

them to interact with their teachers and peers outside the classroom. The online learning platforms facilitate them with the features allowing them to work independently yet share their thoughts through group discussion. Besides, students think that using online learning platforms in learning process is effective since it saves time and effort. This study concluded that students should be able to work with the materials and receive feedback. Successfully implementing online learning into the curriculum requires a well thought-out strategy and a more active approach.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are considered plausible and necessary in order to improve our nation educationally and economically.

1. Organizational innovative climate should be created by the university administrator which must influence lecturers' use intentions of information technology. After information technology is introduced within an organization, if it is supported by high-ranking supervisors, the users' use attitude and intention would be indirectly influenced by the increased use opportunities, and subsequent experience.
2. Also, specific measures to enhance lecturers' computer self-efficacy must be ensured. Therefore, the following are recommended:
3. Technological and vocational schools should systematically cultivate teachers' computer information competency.

References

- Alahmari, A. (2017). The state of distance education in Saudi Arabia. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 18(2), 91–98.
- Ashong, N., & Commander, J. (2012). Students' perceptions on MOOCs: An exploratory study. *Interdisciplinary Journal of e-Skills and Life Long Learning*, 12, 145–162
- Bradley, R., Browne, B., & Kelley, H. (2017). Examining the influence of self-efficacy and self-regulation in online learning. *College Student Journal*, 51(4), 518–530.
- Carver, D. L., & Kosloski Jr., M. F. (2015). Analysis of student perceptions of the psychosocial learning environment in online and face-to-face career and technical education courses. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 16(4), 7–21
- Costa, I. P. E., Faria, H. d. C., & Neto, A. S. (2018). Habits of use of new technologies in children and young people. *Gazeta Médica*, 5(4)
- De Paepe, L., Zhu, C., & Depryck, K. (2018). Online Dutch L2 learning in adult education: Educators' and providers' viewpoint on needs, advantages and disadvantages. *Open Learning*, 33(1), 18–33.
- Dobbs, R., del Carmen, A., & Waid-Lindberg, C. (2017). Students' perceptions of online courses: The effect of online course experience. *The Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 18(1), 98–109
- Hannay, M., & Newvine, T. (2006). Perceptions of distance learning: A comparison of online and traditional learning. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 2(1), 1–11
- Kurt, S. C., & Yildirim, B. (2018). The students' perceptions on blended learning: A Q method analysis. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 18(2), 427–446.
- Nakamura, M. (2017). The state of distance education in Japan. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 18(3), 75–87.

- Peck, L., Stefaniak, J. E., & Shah, S. J. (2018). The correlation of self-regulation and motivation with retention and attrition in distance education. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 19(3), 1–16.
- Tseng, H., & Walsh Jr., E. J. (2016). Blended versus traditional course delivery: Comparing students' motivation, learning outcomes, and preferences. *The Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 17(1), 43–52.

Cite this article:

Author(s), BANKOLE, Adelola Mojisola (RN, RM, ROPHN, BNSc, M.Sc.), Prof. ONIFADE Comfort, (2021). "Students' Perception of and Attitude to Online Teaching During Covid-19 Lockdown at Babcock University". **Name of the Journal:** Euro Global Contemporary Studies Journal, (EGCSJ.COM), P, 47- 57. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5048477>, Issue: 1, Vol.: 1, Article: 5, Month: April, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

